

TEGWANE

Ecological Services

Aquatic Biodiversity Assessment for the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment

Dr Pixley Ka Isaka Seme and Mkhondo

Local Municipalities

Mpumalanga

Compiled for:

November 2025

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Document Control

Report: Aquatic Biodiversity Assessment for the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment

Client: KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment

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Date submitted: 26/11/2025

site CFR02B: October 2025

Illustrations of taxa recorded during the October 2025 survey; ©Christian Fry

Executive Summary

Tegwane Ecological Services (Pty) Ltd was appointed to undertake a comprehensive aquatic biodiversity assessment of the freshwater ecosystems within the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment, located within the Dr Pixley Ka Isaka Seme and Mkhondo Local Municipalities of Mpumalanga Province. This assessment contributes to ongoing efforts to characterise and protect the ecological assets of a region that plays a critical role in maintaining both regional biodiversity and downstream water security.

The purpose of the study was to develop an updated inventory of aquatic biota with a focus on freshwater macroinvertebrates, fish communities, and adult odonata. In addition, the assessment evaluated habitat integrity, geomorphological context, and water quality drivers that influence ecological patterns across the protected area. A wet season field survey was conducted from 23rd to 27th October 2025 and was supported by an extensive desktop review of national and provincial ecological datasets and planning frameworks.

Aquatic ecosystems within the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment were found to be in a largely natural condition. Macroinvertebrate communities reflected high ecological integrity, with SASS5 scores and ASPT values representative of natural to largely natural systems typical of the Eastern Escarpment Mountain region. A total of forty nine taxa were recorded at SASS5 level. Among these, a potentially undescribed species belonging to the Leptophlebiidae (*Aprionyx* sp. nov.) was observed. This highlights the scientific importance of the area as a refuge for unique and potentially endemic aquatic taxa.

Fish communities were consistent with expectations for the Southern Temperate Highveld ecoregion. Six indigenous species were recorded, with the assemblage dominated by Cyprinidae. One species of conservation concern, *Labeobarbus nelspruitensis*, listed as Near Threatened, was confirmed at multiple sites. No alien fish species were detected.

Habitat assessments indicated high structural diversity and intact channel morphology. The sampled rivers ranged from steep mountain headwater streams to upper foothill transitional zones, with sinuous channels, riffle and pool sequences, and coarse bedrock and cobble substrates. Although localised pressures were recorded, including bank erosion related to livestock access and minor disturbance at low water crossings, these impacts were limited in extent and did not significantly alter the overall ecological integrity of the systems.

Water quality remained within natural reference ranges for high altitude mountain systems. Electrical conductivity values were low, pH values were circumneutral to slightly alkaline, and dissolved oxygen concentrations were sufficient to support sensitive aquatic biota. No indicators of nutrient enrichment or other pollution pressures were observed.

The KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment overlaps with several high value freshwater conservation designations. These include Freshwater Ecosystem Priority Areas, Ecological Support Areas within the Mpumalanga Biodiversity Sector Plan, and the Enkangala Grassland Strategic Water Source Area. The Ntombe River is classified as Least Concern and moderately protected, indicating that the system retains high biodiversity value that is dependent on continued careful management. Collectively, these designations emphasise the significance of maintaining the ecological condition of the Sibandlu, Ntombe and Nkipane rivers.

The freshwater ecosystems of the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment support high quality aquatic habitat, natural water quality, and biodiverse macroinvertebrate and fish communities. The presence of a potentially novel macroinvertebrate species and a Near Threatened fish species further elevates the conservation importance of the area. Continued protection of riparian corridors, management of localised erosion, and follow up surveys targeting Ephemeroptera diversity are recommended to strengthen the biodiversity baseline and inform long term ecological management within the protected area.

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Acronyms

ASPT	Average Score Per Taxon
CR	Critically Endangered
DD	Data Deficient
DEA	(former) Department of Environmental Affairs
DO	Dissolved Oxygen
EAP	Environmental Assessment Practitioner
EC	Electrical Conductivity
EPT	Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera, and Trichoptera
ESA	Ecological Support Area
FEPA	Freshwater Ecosystem Priority Area
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSM	Gravel, Sand & Mud
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
LC	Least Concern
MASL	Meters Above Sea Level
NEMA	National Environmental Management Act, 1998 (Act No. 107 of 1998)
NT	Near Threatened
PAOI	Project Area of Influence
PES	Present Ecological State
REMP	River Eco-status Monitoring Programme
SACNASP	South African Council for Natural Scientific Professions
SAIIAE	South African Inventory of Inland Aquatic Ecosystems
SANBI	South African National Biodiversity Institute
SASS5	South African Scoring System 5
SCC	Species of Conservation Concern
SIC	Stones in Current
SWSA	Strategic Water Source Areas
Veg	Vegetation
VU	Vulnerable

Glossary of Terms

Term	Definition
Anthropogenic	An activity originating due to human activity
Aquatic Ecosystem	Ecosystems found in bodies of water that contain low concentrations of dissolved salts, including rivers, lakes, and wetlands.
Aquatic Vegetation	Plant species that grow in or near water, providing essential habitat, food, and oxygen for aquatic life.
Ecological drivers	ecological processes that maintain specific ecosystems and underpin their persistence
Ecosystem Services	The benefits provided by ecosystems, including clean water, flood regulation, and carbon sequestration, that support both human and ecological well-being.
Endemic Species	Species that are native to and found only in a specific location or habitat.
Eutrophication	The process by which a body of water becomes enriched with nutrients, leading to excessive plant growth, oxygen depletion, and loss of biodiversity.
Extent of a watercourse	The outer edge of the 1 in100 year flood line and/or delineated riparian habitat, which ever is the greatest distance, measured from the middle of the watercourse of a river, spring, natural channel, lake or dam.
Indicator Species	Species whose presence, absence, or abundance reflects the health of an ecosystem.
Invasive Species	Non-native species that cause harm to the environment, economy, or human health by outcompeting local species.
Pollution	The introduction of harmful substances (e.g., chemicals, plastics, nutrients) into aquatic environments, negatively impacting biodiversity.
Riparian habitat	Includes the physical structure and associated vegetation of the areas adjacent to a watercourse which are commonly characterised by a high water table sufficient to support vegetation of species with a composition and physical structure distinct from those of adjacent land areas
Species of Conservation Concern (SCC)	All species that are listed under the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List as Near Threatened, Vulnerable, Endangered or Critically Endangered, as well as endemics.

1. Introduction

Tegwane Ecological Services (Pty) Ltd was appointed to undertake an aquatic biodiversity assessment of the freshwater systems within the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment (KPE), located in the Dr Pixley Ka Isaka Seme and Mkhondo Local Municipalities, Mpumalanga Province (Figure 1-1).

The primary objective of the assessment was to develop a comprehensive inventory of aquatic taxa occurring within the KPE, with emphasis on freshwater macroinvertebrates and fish communities. Adult odonata encountered during fieldwork were also recorded to supplement the biodiversity dataset.

To evaluate the ecological condition and potential drivers influencing aquatic biodiversity, a suite of stressor and exposure indicators were assessed. These included *in situ* physico-chemical water quality measurement, channel and geomorphological characterisation, and habitat quality assessments. Field-based observations were supported by a desktop analysis incorporating provincial datasets, and literature describing expected aquatic biota and river system characteristics. A wet-season field survey was conducted from 23rd to 27th October 2025.

Figure 1-1 Locality of the Project Area of Interest (PAOI)

2. Definitions

According to the NWA (1998),

“**riparian habitat**” includes the physical structure and associated vegetation of the areas associated with a watercourse which are commonly characterised by alluvial soils, and which are inundated or flooded to an extent and with a frequency sufficient to support vegetation of species with a composition and physical structure distinct from those of adjacent land areas;

“**watercourse**” means-

- (a) a river or spring;
 - (b) a natural channel in which water flows regularly or intermittently;
 - (c) a wetland lake or dam into which, or from which, water flows: and
 - (d) any collection of water which the Minister may, by notice in the Gazette, declare (to be watercourse,
- and a reference to a watercourse includes, where relevant, its bed and banks.

The following definitions were obtained from DWS (2017) and DWS (2023):

- (i) **"Characteristics of a watercourse"** means the resource quality of a watercourse within the extent of a watercourse.
- (iv) **"Delineation of a wetland and riparian habitat"** means the delineation of wetlands and riparian habitat according to the methodology contained in the Department of Water Affairs and Forestry, 2008 publication: *A Practical Field Procedure for Delineation of Wetlands and Riparian Areas*, or any amended version.
- (viii) **"Extent of a watercourse"** means:
 - (a) The outer edge of the 1 in 100-year flood line or delineated riparian habitat, whichever is the greatest distance, measured from the middle of the watercourse of a river, spring, natural channel, dams, and lakes; and
 - (b) Wetlands (including pans): the delineated boundary (extent) of any wetland or pan.
- (xiii) **"Pans"** refers to any depression collecting water or that is inward draining or a flow-through system with flow contributions from surface water, groundwater, interflow, or combinations thereof.
- (xiv) **"Regulated area of a watercourse"** means:
 - (a) The outer edge of the 1 in 100-year flood line or delineated riparian habitat, whichever is the greatest distance, measured from the middle of the watercourse of a river, spring, natural channel, dams, and lakes;
 - (b) In the absence of a determined 1 in 100-year flood line or riparian area as contemplated in (a) above, the area within 100m distance from the edge of a watercourse, where the edge of the watercourse (excluding flood plains) is the first identifiable annual bank fill flood bench (subject to compliance with section 144 of the National Water Act 36 of 1998);
 - (c) (c) In respect of a wetland: a 500 m radius around the delineated boundary (extent) of any wetland (including pans).

3. Methods

3.1. Desktop Review

As part of the aquatic biodiversity assessment, several geospatial datasets for the were evaluated (Table 3-1).

Table 3-1 Geospatial datasets for the aquatic biodiversity assessment

Geospatial Datasets	Resource
1:50 000 Topographical	Surveyor General
Contour data (5 m)	Surveyor General
Mpumalanga Biodiversity Sector Plan (MBSP)	MTPA (2014)
National Biodiversity Assessment (NBA)	Van Deventer <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Present Ecological State (PES), Ecological Importance (EI) and Ecological Sensitivity (ES) per SQR	DWS (2014)
Satellite imagery	Google Earth Pro
South African Inventory of Inland Aquatic Ecosystems (SAIIAE)	Van Deventer <i>et al.</i> (2019)
South African National Land Cover (SANLC)	SANBI (2008); DEA (2019)
The National Freshwater Ecosystem Priority Areas (NFEPA)	Nel <i>et al.</i> (2011)
The SANBI National Wetland Map 5	Van Deventer <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Vegetation and climate information	Mucina & Rutherford (2006)

3.2. Field Survey

A wet season field survey was conducted on the 23rd to the 27th of October 2025. Sampling points are illustrated in Figure 3-1, which were selected according to accessibility, and to provide a representative sample to characterise the abiotic drivers and biotic communities within the river reach. Site details are presented in Table 3-2.

Figure 3-1 Illustration of the aquatic sampling points within the PAOI

Table 3-2 Site photographs and GPS Coordinates (Photos taken October 2025)

Site CFR01	GPS Coordinate: -27.213621° 30.493017°
Upstream view	Downstream view
Site CFR02A	GPS Coordinate: -27.185069° 30.486301°
Upstream view	Downstream view
Site CFR02B	GPS Coordinate: -27.188238° 30.500058°
Upstream view	Downstream view

Site CFR03	GPS Coordinate: -27.219772° 30.554238°
Upstream view	Downstream view
Site CFR04	GPS Coordinate: -27.254130° 30.591409°
Upstream view	Downstream view
Site CFR05A	GPS Coordinate: -27.250713° 30.531540°
Upstream view	Downstream view

Site CFR05B	GPS Coordinate: -27.248666° 30.536015°
Upstream view	Downstream view
Site CFR06A	GPS Coordinate: -27.290179° 30.547679°
Upstream view	Downstream view
Site CFR06B	GPS Coordinate: -27.289611° 30.548962°
Upstream view	Downstream view

3.2.1. Water Quality

The term “water quality’ characterizes the state of water properties and constituents evaluated against standards and criteria of suitability for human use and ecosystem function. *In situ* water quality analysis was conducted at each site with sufficient surface water. Measuring physico-chemical parameters in rivers provides a snapshot of the health, quality, and sustainability of river ecosystems. These measurements help to monitor and manage water resources, track environmental changes, and identify potential limiting factors that may affect the abundance and diversity of local aquatic biota, as different species of aquatic organisms have specific environmental requirements.

A calibrated Smart Sensor® pH, Electrical Conductivity and Dissolved Oxygen (DO) meter was used during the survey. Physico-chemical parameters recorded include:

- pH
- Electrical Conductivity (EC) ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)
- Dissolved Oxygen (mg/l), and
- Water Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).

3.2.2. Habitat Integrity

Habitat diversity and quality play a crucial role in determining the abundance and composition of local aquatic biota. The habitat integrity of a river refers to the maintenance of a balanced composition of physico-chemical and habitat characteristics and its ability to support and maintain a balanced, diverse, integrated, and adaptive community of organisms (Kleynhans 1996). In this study, habitat assessments included the use of the biotope diversity (Dickens and Graham, 2002; Lowe *et al.*, 2012) to evaluate macroinvertebrate habitat diversity. The index considers sampled habitat. The sampled habitat is broken down into three sub-sections namely Stones-In-Current (SIC), Vegetation (VEG), and Gravel Sand & Mud (GSM).

3.1. Habitat Characterisation

Riparian areas serve as the transition zones between aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems, with vegetation exhibiting traits of both environments. Many plants in these areas thrive in conditions with abundant water and a shallow water table. Due to the availability of water and nutrient-rich alluvial soils, riparian zones are typically highly productive. Tree growth is rapid, and the understory is often dense, supporting a diverse array of shrubs, grasses, and wildflowers. Typical riverine features used for riparian delineations are presented in Figure 3-2. Riparian zones are crucial for maintaining water quality, preventing erosion, providing habitat for wildlife, and supporting biodiversity. They act as natural buffers, filtering pollutants from runoff, stabilizing riverbanks, and offering essential habitats for various plant and animal species. Additionally, they help regulate water temperature and contribute to the overall health of aquatic ecosystems. Classification of river channels was conducted according to Rowntree *et al.*, (2000) and is presented in Table 3-3.

Figure 3-2 Typical cross section of a river channel (DWAf, 2005)

Table 3-3 *Geomorphological Zonation of River Channels (Rowntree et al. 2000)*

Zone	Zone class	Gradient class
Source zone	S	Not specified
Mountain headwater stream	A	> 0.10
Mountain stream	B	0.04 – 0.099
Transitional	C	0.01 – 0.039
Upper foothills	D	0.005 – 0.019
Lower foothills	E	0.001 – 0.005
Lowland river	F	0.0001- 0.0009
Slope (m/m)= Elevation loss/Horizontal distance		
Channel Patterns		
Pattern Type	Description	Typical Setting
Straight	Single, low-sinuosity channel; rare in nature; usually confined or bedrock-controlled.	Headwaters, confined valleys
Sinuuous	Gently winding channel with moderate sinuosity (1.1–1.5).	Transitional zones
Meandering	Highly sinuous, looping channel; single-thread with well-developed point bars.	Low-gradient alluvial plains
Braided	Multiple shifting channels with exposed bars; high sediment load and variable flow.	Steep, sediment-rich rivers
Anastomosing	Multiple stable channels separated by vegetated islands; lower energy than braided.	Floodplains, cohesive banks
Anabranching	Similar to anastomosing but with larger, more permanent branches.	Very low gradient areas

3.1.1. Macroinvertebrate Assessment

In this study, macroinvertebrates were sampled using the qualitative kick sampling method, known as SASS5 (South African Scoring System, version 5) (Dickens and Graham, 2002). Sampled macroinvertebrates were identified to family level using “A Field Guide to Freshwater Macroinvertebrates of Southern Africa” (Fry 2022). Metrics applied to the macroinvertebrate community collected during the study were applied as follows: the number of taxa; sum of sensitivity scores; and the Average Score Per Taxon (ASPT).

3.1.1.1. South African Scoring System version 5

The SASS5 protocol (Dickens and Graham, 2002) is a widely used bioassessment tool for evaluating the ecological health of freshwater systems in South Africa. It is specifically designed to assess the condition of river ecosystems by examining the diversity and abundance of aquatic macroinvertebrates. These organisms are sensitive to changes in water quality, habitat, and pollution, making them effective indicators of environmental health. The protocol involves collecting a representative sample of aquatic macroinvertebrates from various habitats within the river. Each macroinvertebrate taxon is assigned a score based on its sensitivity to pollution and habitat degradation. Taxa that are highly sensitive to pollution receive higher scores, while more tolerant taxa receive lower scores. The total sensitivity score is calculated by summing the scores of all the identified taxa. Additionally, the average score per taxon (ASPT) is calculated, which provides additional insight into the ecological integrity of the system.

3.1.2. Fish Assemblage

An expected species list was generated for the PAOI. The list was created using the DWS Resource Quality Services PESEIS datasets (DWS, 2014), IUCN Freshwater Biodiversity Unit database (IUCN 2024), Skelton (2024), and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF 2025). Nomenclature and global conservation status have been updated according to Skelton (2024) and IUCN (2024). Fish sampling was conducted using electrofishing (SUM electrofishing unit), cast net, and minnow traps. Additionally, local fishermen were interviewed.

4. Limitations

- A single wet season field survey was conducted, limiting the temporal interpretation of ecological conditions
- Macroinvertebrates were identified in the field to lowest level possible.
- Standard rapid assessments were implemented in line with Aquatic Biodiversity Protocols for Ecosystem Environmental Assessment Guidelines (DFFE, 2021).

5. Results

5.1. Desktop Review

A summary of the desktop review for the PAOI is presented in Table 5-1, which highlights relevant ecologically important freshwater landscape features.

Table 5-1 Ecologically important landscape features

Geospatial Dataset	Applicable	Justification	Section
South African Inventory of Inland Aquatic Ecosystems	Yes	According to NBA2018_Rivers database, the Ntombe River runs through the PAOI, which is designated as Least Concern and moderately protected.	5.1.1
Conservation Plan	Yes	The PAOI intersects with areas designated as Ecological Support Area (ESA)	5.1.4
SA Protected Areas Data (SAPAD)	Yes	Yes, designated as the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment	5.1.4
SA Conservation Areas Data (SACAD)	No	The PAOI does not fall a conservation area	5.1.4
National Freshwater Ecosystem Priority Areas	Yes	The PAOI intersects with areas designated as a river FEPA	5.1.5
Strategic Water Source Areas	Yes	The PAOI lies within the Enkangala Grassland SWSA	5.1.6

5.1.1. Freshwater Ecological Setting

The PAOI is situated in the W42C quaternary catchment, within the Pongola-Mtamvuna Water Management Area (WMA) and the Eastern Escarpment Mountains Freshwater Ecoregion (Figure 5-1, Figure 5-2 & Figure 5-3). According to the desktop spatial layers (DWS 2014; Van Deventer, *et al.* 2019; DEA 2025; Open Cycle Maps 2025; and Google Earth 2025), confusion lies around the naming, designation and digitising of the river systems within the PAOI (Ntombe, Kwantombe, and Sibandlu Rivers). For the purposes of this study, naming of the systems follows DEA (2025), Open Cycle maps (2025), and local stakeholders (pers. Comm Filter H.). Freshwater features and naming of systems is presented in Figure 5-4. The PAOI is primarily drained by two rivers, the Ntombe and Sibandlu Rivers, which flow east and eventuate into the Phongolo River at the outlet of the W42C catchment. The Nkipane River was further included in the naming of systems. A single Sub Quaternary Catchment (SQR) has been assessed by DWS (2014), namely the Ntombe River which is represented by the W42C-2205 SQR.

According to Van Deventer, *et al.* (2019), the Ecosystem threat status (ETS) of the Ntombe River ecosystem is listed as Least Concern (LT) (Figure 5-5), indicating a large extent (>60%) to which the river ecosystem type is in its near natural condition. Additionally, the Ntombe/Sibandlu River is listed as Moderately Protect (MP) (Figure 5-6), indicating at least 50%% of its biodiversity target is located in protected areas and in natural or near-natural ecological condition.

According to Mucina and Rutherford (2006), the PAOI is situated within the Grassland Biome, with the upper catchment falling into the Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland and the lower reaches falling into the Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland vegetation units, with a mosaic of Northern Afrotropical Forest within the headwater tributaries (Figure 5-8). The freshwater systems are shaped by these vegetation units, including hydrological behaviour, erosion patterns, and the quality of aquatic habitat.

The Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland, occupying the higher escarpment slopes and plateaus, forms an important headwater catchment zone. Its short, dense montane grass cover promotes effective infiltration, moderates runoff, and supports relatively stable baseflows to downstream systems. However, steep slopes and shallow soils increase sensitivity to erosion where vegetation is disturbed, particularly in areas invaded by *Leucosidea sericea* or where grazing pressure is excessive. These erosive processes contribute sediment to small streams and wetlands, influencing channel morphology and habitat structure.

The Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland, situated at slightly lower elevations with more undulating terrain and broad valley bottoms, contributes to groundwater recharge and the formation of wide seepage zones and wetland valleys. Its tall, forb-rich grasslands provide strong soil binding, helping to maintain slope stability and reduce sediment delivery to watercourses. Deep, well-drained apedal soils support consistent infiltration, although agricultural transformation or overgrazing can elevate runoff, channel incision, and turbidity in tributaries linked to the Phongolo headwaters.

The Northern Afrotropical Forest occurs as sheltered patches along steep tributaries, cascades and waterfalls, where cool, moist microclimates are maintained by perennial water flow. These forested kloofs stabilise slopes, reduce erosion, and buffer stream temperatures through dense canopy cover. The forest margins trap sediments and organic material, enhancing nutrient cycling and providing structurally complex riparian habitat important for aquatic invertebrates, amphibians, and rheophilic fish.

Together, these vegetation units regulate hydrological processes, influence sediment and nutrient dynamics, and provide essential riparian habitat linkages that underpin the ecological integrity of rivers, wetlands and headwater seep systems within the Protected Environment. According to Mucina and Rutherford, (2006), the region has summer rainfall, with mean annual precipitation (MAP) of 902mm (Figure 5-7). According to Schulze *et al.* (2007) the K-factor for soil erodibility ranged from 0.2 to 0.29, indicating a low to moderate erosion potential (Figure 5-9, Table 5-2).

Figure 5-1 Locality of the PAOI within the Pongola-Mtamvuna WMA

Figure 5-2 Locality of the PAOI within the W42C catchment

Figure 5-3 Level 1 Freshwater Ecoregion associated with the PAOI

Figure 5-4 Freshwater features associated with the PAOI

Figure 5-5 Threat Status of the Ntombe River (Van Deventer, et al., 2019) (LT-Least Concern)

Figure 5-6 Protection level of the Ntombe River (Van Deventer, et al., 2019) (MP- Moderately Protected)

Gm 14 Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland

Gm 15 Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland

Figure 5-7 Average rainfall amount (mm) and rainy days (Mucina and Rutherford, 2006)

Table 5-2 Soil erodibility (K-Factor) classification (in: Macfarlane et al., 2014)

Soil Erodibility Class	Soil K-Factor
Very high	> 0.70
High	0.50-0.70
Moderate	0.25-0.50
Low	0.13-0.25
Very low	< 0.13

Figure 5-8 Vegetation Units for the PAOI (Mucina and Rutherford, 2006)

Figure 5-9 Soil Erodibility K-factor (derived from Macfarlane et al., 2014)

5.1.2. Aquatic Biodiversity Sensitivity

According to the environmental screening tool (DEA, 2025), the KPE Project Area of Interest (PAOI) is considered “very high sensitivity” for aquatic biodiversity. This attributed to the presence of Freshwater Ecosystem Priority Areas (FEPA) including rivers, wetland/floodplains, areas designated as an Ecological Support Area (ESA), and the PAOI situated within the Enkangala Grassland Strategic Water Source Area (SWSA) (Figure 5-10).

MAP OF RELATIVE AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY THEME SENSITIVITY

Very High sensitivity	High sensitivity	Medium sensitivity	Low sensitivity
X			

Sensitivity Features:

Sensitivity	Feature(s)
Very High	CBA: Aquatic rivers
Very High	CBA: Wetlands
Very High	ESA: Important subcatchments
Very High	ESA: Strategic Water Source Area
Very High	ESA: Wetland clusters
Very High	ESA: Wetlands
Very High	Wetlands_Channelled valley-bottom
Very High	Wetlands_Depression
Very High	Wetlands_Seep
Very High	Wetlands_Unclassified
Very High	FEPA Subcatchment
Very High	Rivers
Very High	SWSA (sw)_Enkangala Grassland
Very High	SWSA (sw)_Upper Usutu

Figure 5-10 Map of relative aquatic biodiversity theme sensitivity (DEA, 2025) (blue dotted square - PAOI)

5.1.3. Desktop Ecological State

The Present Ecological State (PES), Ecological Importance (EI) & Ecological Sensitivity (ES) was obtained from DWS (2014). The datasets are applied at first level desktop assessments for Ecological Water Resource Monitoring (EWRM). Information obtained was for the W42C- 2205 SQR, which represents the most relevant SQR to the PAOI. At a desktop level, the SQR is in a largely natural state (Table 5-3). This is attributed to minor impacts from agricultural fields within the upper reaches, sedimentation, and vegetation removal. Wetland continuity and high riparian and wetland habitat integrity have resulted in high EI for the SQR. The riverine habitats within the reach have low tolerances to flow modifications, with aquatic biota being highly sensitive to flow and physicochemical modifications resulting in a high ES.

Table 5-3 Desktop Ecological Data for the W42C-2205 SQR

SQR Reach	Class	Justification
PES	Class B (Largely Natural)	Small to moderate modifications to the instream and wetland/riparian habitat continuity, with moderate physico-chemical modifications from reference conditions. Large modifications to instream habitat and flow.
EI	High	Very high EI of instream-wetland and riparian vertebrates (excluding fish), and high % of natural vegetation within these zones. High riparian wetland migration links.
ES	High	Fish communities and macroinvertebrates sensitivity to modification in water chemistry and flow modifications are very high. Low tolerance of instream habitat and vegetation to flow and water level changes.
Comment	The following impacts/activities were identified: Rural in lower reaches, over-grazing, degraded areas, sediments, dryland agriculture, alien invasive plants, roads. Large tributary from Paardeplats Nature Reserve not digitised.	

5.1.4. Conservation Plans and Protected Areas

According to the Mpumalanga Biodiversity Sector Plan (MBSP) (MTPA, 2014), the PAOI is located within an Ecological Support Area (ESA) (Figure 5-11). These areas, while not critical for achieving biodiversity targets, are important for maintaining the functioning of protected areas and Critical Biodiversity Areas (CBAs), as well as for providing essential ecosystem services. ESAs should therefore be preserved in at least a functional and preferably natural state to continue fulfilling their ecological role. They typically include features such as riparian zones, wetland buffers, and ecological corridors. Additionally, the PAOI falls within the SA Protected Areas Data (SAPAD) listed as KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment (Figure 5-12).

Figure 5-11 Mpumalanga Biodiversity Sector Plan associated with the PAOI (MTPA, 2014)

Figure 5-12 South African Protected Areas associated with the PAOI

5.1.5. National Freshwater Ecosystem Priority Areas

The National Freshwater Ecosystem Priority Areas (NFEPA) project provides strategic spatial priorities aimed at conserving South Africa’s freshwater ecosystems and ensuring the sustainable use of water resources (Driver *et al.*, 2011; Nel *et al.*, 2011). These priorities, known as Freshwater Ecosystem Priority Areas (FEPAs), were identified based on various criteria focused on maintaining essential ecological processes and conserving ecosystem types and species linked to rivers, wetlands, and estuaries. The FEPA maps, along with supporting information, contribute to a comprehensive approach for the sustainable and equitable development of South Africa’s limited water resources. They serve as a consistent, nationwide information source, integrating freshwater ecosystem and biodiversity objectives into planning and decision-making. In the context of integrated water resource management, the maps offer guidance on which rivers, wetlands, and estuaries should be preserved in natural or near-natural conditions to support the water resource protection objectives of the National Water Act.

According to the NFEPA atlas, the study area is in a river FEPA (Figure 5-13). River FEPAs protect biodiversity, including threatened and near-threatened fish, and are designated in river reaches currently in good ecological condition (Category A or B). While the FEPA status applies to the specific river reach, the surrounding catchment also needs careful management to maintain this condition. Even rivers in good condition may require interventions, such as alien plant clearing or bank rehabilitation, to secure ecological structure and function before addressing Phase 2 FEPAs or other areas.

Figure 5-13 Illustration of the NFEPA's associated with the PAOI (derived from Nel *et al.* 2011)

5.1.6. Strategic Water Source Areas

Water Source Areas (WSAs) have traditionally been defined based on their ability to generate significant volumes of runoff that support downstream lowland areas. A total of 21 Strategic Water Source Areas (SWSA) have been identified and delineated in South Africa. These areas, covering 8% of South Africa, contribute 50% of the country's mean annual runoff. The SWSA were included in the National Water Resources Strategy as regions that require protection to ensure water security. According to Le Maitre *et al.*, (2018), the PAOI lies within the delineated SWSA Enkangala Grassland (Figure 5-14).

Figure 5-14 Strategic Water Source Areas associated with the PAOI (derived from: Le Maitre *et al.*, 2018)

5.1.7. Fish Assemblage

An expected fish species list was generated based on a literature review [DWS (2014), Skelton (2024), and GBIF (2025)]. The ichthyofaunal ecoregion is classified as the Southern Temperate Highveld (Figure 5-15). The river systems within the PAOI ranges from mountain head water stream, mountain to upper foothills with several transitional zones. According to literature, 7 indigenous fish species were expected (Table 5-4). Cyprinidae form the dominant expect group, with 57% of the community. Two species of Conservational Concern were expected, *Chiloglanis emarginatus* (VU), and *Labeobarbus nelspruitensis* (NT).

Figure 5-15 Freshwater ecoregion (Abell et al., 2008)

Table 5-4 Expected fish species list for the for the W42C catchment, Southern Temperature Ecoregion and site specific FROC

Family	Species	Common	Frequency of Occurrence			Overall Intolerance Rating	IUCN Status	Habitat Preferences & Biology (Skelton, 2001; IUCN, 2015)
			CFR05B	CFR01, CFR06B	CFR03, CFR04, CFR05A			
Amphiliidae	<i>Anoplopterus</i> sp. 'southern stargazer'	Mountain catfishes	0	2	5	4,8	Least Concern	Clear, flowing water with rocky substrate. Feeds on insects and other small organisms off rock surfaces. Breeds in summer.
Cyprinidae	<i>Enteromius crocodilensis</i>	Barbs	5	5	5	4,2	Least Concern	Inhabits clear sheltered pools, and riffles in clear rocky streams
Mochokidae	<i>Chiloglanis anoterus</i>	Suckermouth Catlets	0	5	5	4,8	Least Concern	Flowing water over cobbles and in shoots
Mochokidae	<i>Chiloglanis emarginatus</i>	Suckermouth Catlets	0	0	1	5	Vulnerable	Flowing water over cobbles and in shoots
Cyprinidae	<i>Labeobarbus marequensis</i>	Large scale Yellowfish	0	1	5	2,6	Least Concern	Favours flowing waters of perennial rivers. Omnivore. Breeds in spring and summer.
Cyprinidae	<i>Labeobarbus polylepis</i>	Small scale yellowfish	0	0	3	3,1	Least Concern	A cool-water species. Perennial rivers and dams. Omnivore. Breeds in spring and summer.
Cyprinidae	<i>Labeobarbus nelspruitensis</i>	Chiselmouths	0	1	5	3,1	Near Threatened	Full migrant found in larger escarpment streams where there are good water flows and rocky substrates
Frequency of Occurrence (FROC) 0- unlikely occur 5- highly probable to occur								

5.2. Survey Results

5.2.1. Water Quality

Basic physico-chemical parameters were measured at KPE river sites in October 2025 to assess spatial variation in water quality and biotic interpretation, results are presented in Table 5-5.

- pH levels from systems along the Ntombe and Sibandlu Rivers ranged from 7.7 to 8.1, indicating alkaline pH levels. Slight acidic levels were recorded on the Nkipane (site CFR06B).
- The Electrical Conductivity (EC) levels indicated limited contribution of dissolved ions from surrounding geology, and well as limited inputs from anthropogenic activities. The EC levels ranged from 30 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at CFR01 to at 53 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at CFR06B.
- Dissolved Oxygen (DO) levels were lowest at sites sampled in the morning (early morning oxygen stress), with an increase in DO recorded at sites sampled later in the day. Results indicate relatively low biological/chemical oxygen demand within the system.
- Temperature variation reflects time-of-day sampling: CFR01/CFR05A (early morning) was cooler, while CFR02B/CFR04/CFR06B (midday) showed elevated temperatures due to diurnal warming.

Table 5-5 *In situ water quality results for the October 2025 survey*

Parameter	Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	Time of day (hh:mm)	pH	EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	DO (mg/L)	Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
CFR01	24/10/25	09:26	8.1	30	4.7	18.2
CFR02A	24/10/25	13:50	7.9	32	4.9	18.9
CFR02B	24/10/25	15:40	7.9	45	5.2	23.5
CFR03	25/10/25	8:20	7.7	43	4.9	19.3
CFR04	25/10/25	16:23	7.7	45	5.3	25.8
CFR05A	26/10/2025	6:27	7.7	34	5.1	18.1
CFR06B	26/10/25	14:50	6.7	53	5.3	21.4

5.2.2. Geomorphological Zonation

A summary of the geomorphological features of the river reaches is presented in Table 5-6. The assessed reaches fall within the Eastern Escarpment Mountains freshwater ecoregion and are characteristic of high-gradient mountain headwater streams transitioning into upper foothill zones (Figure 5-16 and Figure 5-17). These systems exhibit steep to moderate slopes, confined valleys, and a mixture of bedrock-controlled and alluvial channel sections.

Within the uppermost sites, particularly CFR01, CFR02A and CFR02B, the channels are strongly influenced by bedrock and coarse cobble substrates. These reaches display steep gradients, high hydraulic energy, and well-developed riffle and cascade habitats. As the river descends into lower elevation reaches such as CFR03, CFR05A and CFR04, alluvial processes become more prominent. This results in increased gravel, sand and finer sediment deposition, with channel morphology transitioning into broader pool-riffle-glide sequences. The shift from bedrock-dominated to alluvial substrates provides a wider variety of biotopes that support more diverse macroinvertebrate assemblages, which aligns with the higher SASS5 scores recorded in the lower Sibandlu and Ntombe sites.

Channel pattern was predominantly sinuous across most sites, consistent with moderately confined valleys and alternating bedrock and alluvial controls (Rowntree et al. 2000; Rowntree and Ziervogel 1999). Meandering patterns occurred where gradients decreased and valley floors widened, as seen at CFR03, CFR05A and CFR04. These planform changes reflect a natural downstream continuum of decreasing slope, reduced stream power and increasing sediment storage.

Reach types varied from cascade-dominated sections in the steep upper tributaries to well-developed pool-riffle and riffle-glide sequences in the transitional foothill zones. The rejuvenated bedrock fall and chute-riffle system at CFR06B reflects localised knick-point formation and rapid incision, which generates highly aerated flow and specialised rheophilic habitats. Collectively, these geomorphological patterns create a mosaic of hydraulic conditions, substrate diversity, and microhabitats that underpin the distribution of sensitive aquatic taxa recorded during the survey.

Although all sites were classified as ephemeral in the desktop hydrological layer, field evidence indicates that several of these reaches maintain flow for extended periods during the wet season due to shallow groundwater contributions and orographic rainfall typical of the escarpment. The presence of flow-dependent macroinvertebrates, such as Heptageniidae and Leptophlebiidae, supports the interpretation that these channels behave as seasonally perennial systems in their upper sections during the sampling period.

Table 5-6 Geomorphological features of each site

Site	CFR01	CF02A	CFR02B	CFR03	CFR06B	CFR05A	CFR05B	CFR04
River	Sibandlu	Sibandlu Trib	Sibandlu Trib	Sibandlu	Nkipane	Ntombe	Ntombe Trib	Ntombe
Elevation (m)	1577	1697	1525	1407	1355	1353	1351	1221
Geomorph Zone	Mountain Stream	Mountain headwater stream	Upper foothills	Transitional to upper foothills	Rejuvenated bedrock fall/cascade	Transitional to upper foothills	Mountain stream	Upper foothills
Strahler Order	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	3
Hydrological type	Ephemeral	Ephemeral	Ephemeral	Ephemeral	Ephemeral	Ephemeral	Ephemeral	Ephemeral
Lateral mobility	Limited	Limited	Limited	Limited	Limited	Limited	Limited	Limited
Channel pattern	Sinuuous	Sinuuous	Sinuuous	Meandering	Sinuuous	Meandering	Sinuuous	Meandering
Reach type	Pool-riffle	Cascade to pool/riffle	Glide-pool-riffle	Pool-riffle-glide	Pool-chute-riffle	Riffle-glide-pool	Pool-riffle	Run-riffle-pool

Figure 5-16 Elevation profile of the river segment and sampled sites within the PAOI (~22 km of Sibandlu River)

Figure 5-17 Elevation profile of the river segment and sampled sites within the PAOI (~34 km of Ntombe River)

Boulder and alluvial deposits within the mountain stream at site CFR01

Riffle-pool habitat with bedrock control reach at site CFR01

*Mountain headwater stream within Northern Afrotemperate Forest at site CFR02A, where *Aprionyx* sp. nov. was observed*

Rejuvenation zone in the Sibandlu reach above site CFR03

Rejuvenated bedrock fall/cascades at site CFR06B

Source zone of the Nkipane River, site CFR06A

5.2.3. SASS5 Biotopes

SASS5 biotope results for the sampled sites are presented in Table 5-7 and Figure 5-18. Most sites supported a moderately diverse range of macroinvertebrate biotopes, generally exceeding fifty percent biotope richness. The exception was sites CF02A and CFR02B, where biotope diversity was low. This reduced diversity is considered natural for steep, confined mountain headwater streams, where high gradients, coarse substrates and narrow channel margins limit the development of vegetation, depositional habitats and slackwater areas. As a result, these upper sites are naturally dominated by stones biotopes and bedrock exposures.

Vegetation biotopes were largely absent in the upper reaches of the Sibandlu and Nkipane systems, reflecting the narrow, incised channel morphology, limited floodplain development and higher hydraulic energy typical of the mountain stream and mountain headwater geomorphological zones. Downstream, an increase in vegetation-associated biotopes was recorded at CFR04, although these remained limited in taxonomic and structural diversity, consisting mainly of Phragmites reeds and marginal roots. This shift corresponds with the transition into broader foothill reaches where lower gradients and higher alluvial deposition create more stable margins conducive to plant establishment.

Across all sites, stones biotopes were the dominant habitat sampled, with both stones-in-current and stones-out-of-current consistently present. These habitats are strongly associated with higher macroinvertebrate diversity and provide essential surfaces for colonisation by flow-dependent taxa such as Heptageniidae, Leptophlebiidae and Hydropsychidae. The consistent availability of these biotopes throughout the study area supports the high ecological integrity recorded in the SASS results.

Gravel, sand and mud (GSM) biotopes were present at all sites, although they were generally less dominant than stones. Their presence reflects natural depositional processes and the gradual downstream increase in alluvial material described in the geomorphology section. Importantly, GSM biotopes did not show evidence of excessive fine sediment loading or smothering, which would typically indicate catchment disturbance or erosion. Instead, their distribution appears consistent with natural sediment transport patterns associated with the transition from steep mountain reaches to more moderate foothill zones.

Overall, the biotope patterns align well with the geomorphological continuum of the river systems. Upper sites are characterised by high-energy, substrate-controlled habitats with limited marginal development, while downstream sites display slightly greater habitat heterogeneity and increased vegetated margins. These natural patterns provide the structural basis for the macroinvertebrate assemblages recorded during the survey and contribute to the high ecological condition observed across the freshwater ecosystems of the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment.

Table 5-7 *Biotope scores representing sampling habitat for macroinvertebrates (October 2025)*

Biotopes	Sibandlu				Nkipane	Ntombe	
	CFR01	CF02A	CFR02B	CFR03	CFR06B	CFR05A	CFR04
Stones in Current	5	1	3	4	4	5	4
Stones out of Current	4	1	2	4	4	5	4
Bedrock	4	2	1	3	4	5	5
Stones	13	4	6	11	12	15	13
Aquatic Vegetation	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Marg Veg in Current	0	1	0	0	1	1	2
Marg Veg out of Current	0	1	0	0	2	2	3

Biotopes	Sibandlu				Nkipane	Ntombe	
	CFR01	CF02A	CFR02B	CFR03	CFR06B	CFR05A	CFR04
Veg	0	2	0	0	3	3	5
Gravel	4	0	2	4	3	1	3
Sand	4	0	2	4	3	4	3
Mud	4	2	2	2	2	3	3
GSM	12	2	6	10	8	8	9
Total (x)	25	8	12	21	23	26	27
Biotope %	56%	18%	27%	47%	51%	58%	60%
Geomorphological Zone	Mountain Stream	Mountain headwater stream	Upper foothills	Transitional to upper foothills	Rejuvenated bedrock fall/cascade	Transitional to upper foothills	Mountain stream

Figure 5-18 Graphical representation of biotopes sampled

5.2.4. Macroinvertebrate Community

Macroinvertebrate results for the October 2025 survey are presented in Table 5-8. Overall, the results demonstrate a diverse and well-structured macroinvertebrate community across most sampled sites. Patterns in SASS5 score, number of taxa and ASPT values indicate that water quality was not a limiting factor for macroinvertebrate diversity. Instead, variation in macroinvertebrate assemblages was primarily driven by habitat availability and biotope diversity, as reflected in the biotope suitability scores.

According to the Eastern Escarpment Mountains biological bands (Dallas 2007), sites CFR01, CFR05A and CFR04 were classified as near natural (Class A), indicating minimal ecological disturbance and high habitat integrity. Sites CFR02B, CFR03 and CFR06B fell within the largely natural category (Class B), reflecting slight but still natural variation in habitat structure along the mountain-to-foothill gradient. These results are consistent with the predominance of stones biotopes, clean substrates and clear, well-oxygenated water observed during the survey.

The Class D result at CF02A does not reflect degraded water quality but is instead attributed to natural limitations at this steep, ephemeral, bedrock-controlled headwater site. Very limited surface water, reduced hydraulic diversity and the scarcity of suitable SASS5 sampling habitats (as indicated by the extremely low biotope suitability score of 18 percent) resulted in a naturally

low number of taxa. Such sites typically fall outside the ideal application range of SASS5 and therefore produce artificially depressed scores. The presence of several flow-sensitive taxa despite these limitations further supports the interpretation that water quality remains natural.

A notable finding of the survey was the observation of a potentially undescribed species of Leptophlebiidae (*Aprionyx* sp. nov.), confirmed through personal communication with Helen James. Members of this family are often associated with high-quality, oxygen-rich mountain streams, and the presence of a possible novel species underscores the conservation and scientific importance of the KwaMandlangampisi aquatic systems. A follow-up survey specifically targeting Ephemeroptera is recommended to collect voucher specimens and confirm the taxonomic status of the species.

A complete list of taxa collected during the survey are presented in Table 5-9 and Table 5-10.

Table 5-8 Macroinvertebrate results from the October 2025 survey

	Sibandlu				Nkipane	Ntombe	
	CFR01	CF02A	CFR02B	CFR03	CFR06B	CFR05A	CFR04
SASS5 Score	172	62	78	157	143	188	211
No. of Taxa	24	11	12	24	24	29	29
ASPT	7,2	5,6	6,5	6,5	6,0	6,5	7,3
Ecological Category*	A	D	B	B	B	A	A
Biotope Suitability	56%	18%	27%	47%	51%	58%	60%

ASPT- Average Score Per Taxon

According to Biological Bands for the:
 Eastern Escarpment Mountains – Upper zones (Dallas, 2007)

Aprionyx sp. nov. observed at site CFR02A

Table 5-9 Macroinvertebrate results for the Sibandlu catchment

Sibandlu River	QV	CFR01				CFR02A				CFR02B				CFR03			
		ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T
PORIFERA (Sponge)	5																
COELENTERATA (Cnidaria)	1																
TURBELLARIA (Flatworms)	3					A			A								
ANNELIDA																	
Oligochaeta (Earthworms)	1					A			A							A	A
Hirudinea (Leeches)	3																
CRUSTACEA																	
Amphipoda (Scuds)	13																
Potamonautidae* (Crabs)	3	B		A	B	1			1			A	A	A		A	A
Atyidae (Freshwater Shrimps)	8																
Palaemonidae (Freshwater Prawns)	10																
HYDRACARINA (Mites)	8	A			A												
PLECOPTERA (Stoneflies)																	
Notonemouridae	14																
Pertidae	12									A			A	A			A
EPHEMEROPTERA (Mayflies)																	
Baetidae 1sp	4																
Baetidae 2 sp	6			B										A			
Baetidae > 2 sp	12	B			B											B	B
Caenidae (Squaregills/Cainflies)	6	A		B	B					A		A	B	A		A	B
Ephemeridae	15																
Heptageniidae (Flatheaded mayflies)	13	1			1												
Leptophlebiidae (Prongills)	9	B		B	B	B			B					B		A	B
Oligoneuridae (Brushlegged mayflies)	15																
Polymitarcyidae (Pale Burrowers)	10																

Sibandlu River	QV	CFR01				CFR02A				CFR02B				CFR03			
		ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T
Prosopistomatidae (Water specs)	15																
Teloganodidae SWC (Spiny Crawlers)	12																
Tricorythidae (Stout Crawlers)	9	B			B					A			A	B			
ODONATA (Dragonflies & Damselflies)																	
Calopterygidae ST,T (Demoiselles)	10																
Chlorocyphidae (Jewels)	10													A			A
Synlestidae (Chlorolestidae)(Sylphs)	8	A		A	A												
Coenagrionidae (Sprites and blues)	4																
Lestidae (Emerald Damselflies/Spreadwings)	8																
Platycnemidae (Stream Damselflies)	10	1			1												
Protoneturidae (Threadwings)	8																
Aeshnidae (Hawkers & Emperors)	8	A			A					A			A	A			A
Macromiidae (Cruisers)	8																
Gomphidae (Clubtails)	6	A		B	B									A		B	B
Libellulidae (Darters/Skimmers)	4											A	A	A			A
LEPIDOPTERA (Aquatic Caterpillars/Moths)																	
Crambidae (Pyralidae)	12																
HEMIPTERA (Bugs)																	
Belostomatidae* (Giant water bugs)	3																
Corixidae* (Water boatmen)	3											A	A				
Gerridae* (Pond skaters/Water striders)	5																
Hydrometridae* (Water measurers)	6																
Naucoridae* (Creeping water bugs)	7	1		1	A											A	A
Nepidae* (Water scorpions)	3																

Sibandlu River	QV	CFR01				CFR02A				CFR02B				CFR03			
		ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T
Notonectidae* (Backswimmers)	3																
Pleidae* (Pygmy backswimmers)	4													H			
Veliidae/M...veliidae* (Ripple bugs)	5					A	B		B							A	A
MEGALOPTERA (Fishflies, Dobsonflies & Alderflies)																	
Corydalidae (Fishflies & Dobsonflies)	8																
Sialidae (Alderflies)	6																
TRICHOPTERA (Caddisflies)																	
Dipseudopsidae	10																
Ecnomidae	8																
Hydropsychidae 1 sp	4					1			1								
Hydropsychidae 2 sp	6	B			B					B			B	B			B
Hydropsychidae > 2 sp	12																
Philopotamidae	10																
Polycentropodidae	12																
Psychomyiidae/Xiphocentronidae	8																
Cased caddis:																	
Barbarochthonidae SWC	13																
Calamoceratidae ST	11																
Glossosomatidae SWC	11																
Hydroptilidae	6													A			A
Hydrosalpingidae SWC	15																
Lepidostomatidae	10			A	A		A		A								
Leptoceridae	6													A			A
Petrothrincidae SWC	11																
Pisuliidae	10																
Sericostomatidae SWC	13																

Sibandlu River		QV	CFR01				CFR02A				CFR02B				CFR03			
Taxon			ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T
COLEOPTERA (Beetles)																		
Dytiscidae/Noteridae* (Diving beetles)	5																	
Elmidae/Dryopidae* (Riffle beetles)	8	A			A										A			
Gyrinidae* (Whirligig beetles)	5	B		A	B				B	B	B			B	A			
Halplidae* (Crawling water beetles)	5																	
Scirtidae (Marsh beetles)	12						B	A		B								
Hydraenidae* (Minute moss beetles)	8														A		1	A
Hydrophilidae* (Water scavenger beetles)	5														1			1
Limnichidae (Marsh-Loving Beetles)	10																	
Psephenidae (Water Pennies)	10	A			A										A		A	A
DIPTERA (Flies)																		
Athericidae (Snipe flies)	10																	
Blepharoceridae (Mountain midges)	15	1			1						1			1				
Ceratopogonidae (Biting midges)	5	1			1								A	A			A	A
Chironomidae (Midges)	2	B		B	B								B	B			A	A
Culicidae* (Mosquitoes)	1	1			1													
Dixidae* (Dixid midge)	10																1	1
Empididae (Dance flies)	6														1			1
Ephydriidae (Shore flies)	3																	
Muscidae (House flies, Stable flies)	1	1			1													
Psychodidae (Moth flies)	1																	
Simuliidae (Blackflies)	5	A			A		A			A	A				A			A
Syrphidae* (Rat tailed maggots)	1																	
Tabanidae (Horse flies)	5																	
Tipulidae (Crane flies)	5	A			A		A			A					1			1
GASTROPODA (Snails)																		

Sibandlu River	QV	CFR01				CFR02A				CFR02B				CFR03			
		ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T
Ampularidae	5																
Ancylidae (Limpets)	6									1							
Bulininae*	3																
Hydrobiidae*	3																
Lymnaeidae* (Pond snails)	3																
Physidae* (Pouch snails)	3																
Planorbinae* (Orb snails)	3																
Thiaridae* (=Melanidae)	3																
Viviparidae* ST	5																
Bivalves																	
Corbiculidae (Clams)	5																
Etheriidae (Freshwater Oysters)																	
Sphaeriidae (Pill clams)	3																
Unionidae (Perly mussels)	6																
SASS Score		162	0	62	172	47	27	5	62	72	0	23	78	147	0	84	157
No. of Taxa		23	0	10	24	9	3	1	11	9	0	6	12	22	0	13	24
ASPT		7,0	0	6,2	7,2	5,2	9,0	5,0	5,6	8,0	0	3,8	6,5	6,7	0	6,5	6,5

Notes on Taxa

Baetidae:
Acanthiops sp.
Demoulinia sp.
Heptageniidae:
Afronurus sp.
Hydropsychidae:
Cheumatopsyche afra type
Leptophlebiidae:
Aprionyx sp.
Veliidae:
Rhagovelia sp.
 Gyrimidae:
Aulonogyrus sp.

Saldidae
Leptophlebiidae:
Adenophlebia
Sylvatica
Aprionyx sp. nov

Baetidae:
Acanthiops sp.
Baetis harrisoni
Demoulinia sp.
Dabulamanzia sp.

Baetidae:
Acanthiops sp.
Baetis harrisoni
Demoulinia sp.
Leptophlebiidae:
Euthraulius sp.
Heptageniidae:
Afronurus sp.
Notonurus sp.
Hydropsychidae:
Cheumatopsyche thomasseti type
Hydropsyche longifurca

Sibandlu River	QV	CFR01				CFR02A				CFR02B				CFR03			
		ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T	ST	VEG	GS M	T

Veliidae:
Rhagovelia sp.
Helotrephidae
Gyrinidae:
Aulonogyrus sp.
Libellulidae
Zygonyx sp.
Gomphidae
Onychogomphus sp.
Paragomphus sp.

Table 5-10 Macroinvertebrate results for the Nkipane and Ntombe rivers

Taxon	QV	CFR06B				CFR05A				CFR04			
		ST	VEG	GSM	T	ST	VEG	GSM	T	ST	VEG	GSM	T
PORIFERA (Sponge)	5												
COELENTERATA (Cnidaria)	1												
TURBELLARIA (Flatworms)	3	A			A			A					
ANNELIDA													
Oligochaeta (Earthworms)	1						1	1		1	A	A	
Hirudinea (Leeches)	3												
CRUSTACEA													
Amphipoda (Scuds)	13												
Potamonautidae* (Crabs)	3	A			A			A		A		A	
Atyidae (Freshwater Shrimps)	8												
Palaemonidae (Freshwater Prawns)	10												
HYDRACARINA (Mites)	8				A		A	B		A		A	B
PLECOPTERA (Stoneflies)													
Notonemouridae	14												
Perlidae	12				B			B		1			1

Taxon	QV	CFR06B				CFR05A				CFR04			
		ST	VEG	GSM	T	ST	VEG	GSM	T	ST	VEG	GSM	T
EPHEMEROPTERA (Mayflies)													
Baetidae 1sp	4							A					
Baetidae 2 sp	6	B	A		B		A					B	
Baetidae > 2 sp	12					B			B	B			B
Caenidae (Squaregills/Cainflies)	6					A	A		B			A	A
Ephemeridae	15												
Heptageniidae (Flatheaded mayflies)	13					B			B	A	A		B
Leptophlebiidae (Prongills)	9	A			A	B		A	B	B			B
Oligoneuridae (Brushlegged mayflies)	15												
Polymitarcyidae (Pale Burrowers)	10												
Prosopistomatidae (Water specs)	15												
Teloganodidae SWC (Spiny Crawlers)	12												
Tricorythidae (Stout Crawlers)	9					A			A	A			A
ODONATA (Dragonflies & Damselflies)													
Calopterygidae ST,T (Demoiselles)	10												
Chlorocyphidae (Jewels)	10	A			A								
Synlestidae (Chlorolestidae)(Sylphs)	8		1		1								
Coenagrionidae (Sprites and blues)	4						A		A		A		A
Lestidae (Emerald Damselflies/Spreadwings)	8												
Platycnemidae (Stream Damselflies)	10	1			1								
Protoneuridae (Threadwings)	8												
Aeshnidae (Hawkers & Emperors)	8					1			1	A			A
Macromiidae (Cruisers)	8												
Gomphidae (Clubtails)	6	A			A	A		A	B			A	A
Libellulidae (Darters/Skimmers)	4					A			A			A	A
LEPIDOPTERA (Aquatic Caterpillars/Moths)													
Crambidae (Pyralidae)	12									1			1

Taxon	QV	CFR06B				CFR05A				CFR04			
		ST	VEG	GSM	T	ST	VEG	GSM	T	ST	VEG	GSM	T
HEMIPTERA (Bugs)													
Belostomatidae* (Giant water bugs)	3												
Corixidae* (Water boatmen)	3	A	A		B			A	A			A	A
Gerridae* (Pond skaters/Water striders)	5		A		A								
Hydrometridae* (Water measurers)	6												
Naucoridae* (Creeping water bugs)	7			A	A		1		1		A		A
Nepidae* (Water scorpions)	3						A		A		A		A
Notonectidae* (Backswimmers)	3		A		A								
Pleidae* (Pygmy backswimmers)	4		1		1								
Veliidae/M...veliidae* (Ripple bugs)	5		A		A		1		1	A	A		B
MEGALOPTERA (Fishflies, Dobsonflies & Alderflies)													
Corydalidae (Fishflies & Dobsonflies)	8												
Sialidae (Alderflies)	6												
TRICHOPTERA (Caddisflies)													
Dipseudopsidae	10												
Ecnomidae	8												
Hydropsychidae 1 sp	4												
Hydropsychidae 2 sp	6	A			A								
Hydropsychidae > 2 sp	12									B			B
Philopotamidae	10	A			A					B			B
Polycentropodidae	12												
Psychomyiidae/Xiphocentronidae	8												
Cased caddis:													
Barbarochthonidae SWC	13												
Calamoceratidae ST	11												
Glossosomatidae SWC	11												
Hydroptilidae	6					A			A				

Taxon	QV	CFR06B				CFR05A				CFR04			
		ST	VEG	GSM	T	ST	VEG	GSM	T	ST	VEG	GSM	T
Hydrosalpingidae SWC	15												
Lepidostomatidae	10												
Leptoceridae	6					A	A		A	A	B		B
Petrothrincidae SWC	11												
Pisuliidae	10												
Sericostomatidae SWC	13												
COLEOPTERA (Beetles)													
Dytiscidae/Noteridae* (Diving beetles)	5		1										
Elmidae/Dryopidae* (Riffle beetles)	8					B		1	B	A			A
Gyrinidae* (Whirligig beetles)	5	B				A			A	A	A		B
Halplidae* (Crawling water beetles)	5												
Scirtidae (Marsh beetles)	12	A											
Hydraenidae* (Minute moss beetles)	8												
Hydrophilidae* (Water scavenger beetles)	5												
Limnichidae (Marsh-Loving Beetles)	10										1		1
Psephenidae (Water Pennies)	10					A			A	A			A
DIPTERA (Flies)													
Athericidae (Snipe flies)	10	1				A			A			1	1
Blepharoceridae (Mountain midges)	15												
Ceratopogonidae (Biting midges)	5	A								A			
Chironomidae (Midges)	2	A	A	A		B		A	B	B			
Culicidae* (Mosquitoes)	1												
Dixidae* (Dixid midge)	10							1	1				
Empididae (Dance flies)	6												
Ephydriidae (Shore flies)	3												
Muscidae (House flies, Stable flies)	1	1											1
Psychodidae (Moth flies)	1												

Taxon	QV	CFR06B				CFR05A				CFR04			
		ST	VEG	GSM	T	ST	VEG	GSM	T	ST	VEG	GSM	T
Simuliidae (Blackflies)	5	B			B	A			A	A			A
Syrphidae* (Rat tailed maggots)	1												
Tabanidae (Horse flies)	5					1			1			1	1
Tipulidae (Crane flies)	5							A	A			1	1
GASTROPODA (Snails)													
Ampularidae	5												
Ancylidae (Limpets)	6												
Bulininae*	3												
Hydrobiidae*	3												
Lymnaeidae* (Pond snails)	3												
Physidae* (Pouch snails)	3												
Planorbinae* (Orb snails)	3												
Thiaridae* (=Melanidae)	3												
Viviparidae* ST	5												
Bivalves													
Corbiculidae (Clams)	5												
Etheriidae (Freshwater Oysters)													
Sphaeriidae (Pill clams)	3												
Unionidae (Perly mussels)	6												
SASS Score		106	41	9	143	150	47	46	188	154	54	54	211
No. of Taxa		17	9	2	24	21	8	9	29	19	9	10	29
ASPT		6,2	4,6	4,5	6,0	7,1	5,9	5,1	6,5	8,1	6,0	5,4	7,3

Notes on Taxa

Baetidae:
Acanthiops sp.
Demoulinia sp.
Hydropsychidae:
Cheumatopsyche thomasseti type
Hydropsyche longifurca
Gerridae:

Baetidae:
Acanthiops sp.
Baetis harrisoni
Demoulinia sp.
Labiobaetis sp.
Heptageniidae:
Afronurus sp.

Baetidae:
Acanthiops sp.
Baetis harrisoni
Demoulinia sp.
Labiobaetis sp.
Heptageniidae:
Afronurus sp.

Taxon	QV	CFR06B				CFR05A				CFR04			
		ST	VEG	GSM	T	ST	VEG	GSM	T	ST	VEG	GSM	T
		<i>Eurymetra natalensis</i> Veliidae: <i>Xiphoveloidea</i> sp. Notonectidae: <i>Enithares</i> sp. Gyrinidae: <i>Dineutus</i> sp. <i>Aulonogyrus</i> sp. Dytiscidae: Laccophilini Platycnemidae: <i>Allocnemis leucosticta</i> Libellulidae: <i>Zygonyx</i> sp. Gomphidae: <i>Paragomphus</i> sp. Ceratopogonidae: Forcipomyiinae <i>Atrichopogon</i> sp.				Hydropsychidae: <i>Cheumatopsyche afra</i> type <i>Hydropsyche longifurca</i> Micronectidae Nepidae: <i>Ranatra</i> sp. Veliidae: <i>Rhagovelia</i> sp. <i>Xiphoveloidea</i> sp. Helotrephidae Gyrinidae: <i>Aulonogyrus</i> sp. Gomphidae: <i>Paragomphus</i> sp.				<i>Notonurus</i> sp. Hydropsychidae: <i>Cheumatopsyche thomasseti</i> type <i>Hydropsyche longifurca</i> <i>Macrostemum capense</i> <i>Polymorphanisus</i> sp. Nepidae: <i>Ranatra</i> sp. Veliidae: <i>Rhagovelia</i> sp. <i>Xiphoveloidea</i> sp. Helotrephidae Gyrinidae: <i>Gyrinus</i> sp. Libellulidae: <i>Zygonyx</i> sp. Gomphidae: <i>Paragomphus</i> sp.			

Table 5-11 Total taxa recorded during the survey (October 2025)

	CFR0 1	CF02 A	CFR02 B	CFR0 3	CFR06 B	CFR05 A	CFR0 4	Total Occurrences
Porifera (sponge)								0
Coelenterata (cnidaria)								0
Turbellaria (flatworms)		A			A	A		3
Annelida								0
Oligochaeta (earthworms)		A		A		1	A	4
Hirudinea (leeches)								0
Crustacea								0
Amphipoda (scuds)								0
Potamonautidae* (crabs)	B	1	A	A	A	A	A	7
Atyidae (freshwater shrimps)								0
Palaemonidae (freshwater prawns)								0
Hydracarina (mites)	A					B	B	3
Plecoptera (stoneflies)								0
Notonemouridae								0
Perlidae			A	A		B	1	4
Ephemeroptera (mayflies)								0
Baetidae 1sp								0
Baetidae 2 sp					B			1
Baetidae > 2 sp	B			B		B	B	4
Caenidae (squaregills/cainflies)	B		B	B		B	A	5
Ephemeridae								0
Heptageniidae (Flatheaded mayflies)	1					B	B	3
Leptophlebiidae (prongills)	B	B		B	A	B	B	6
Oligoneuridae (Brushlegged mayflies)								0
Polymitarcyidae (pale burrowers)								0
Prosopistomatidae (Water specs)								0
Teloganodidae swc (spiny crawlers)								0
Tricorythidae (stout crawlers)	B		A			A	A	4
Odonata (dragonflies & damselflies)								0
Calopterygidae st,t (demoiselles)								0
Chlorocyphidae (jewels)				A	A			2
Synlestidae (chlorolestidae)(sylphs)	A				1			2
Coenagrionidae (Sprites and blues)						A	A	2
Lestidae (emerald damselflies/spreadwings)								0
Platycnemidae (stream damselflies)	1				1			2
Protoneuridae (threadwings)								0
Aeshnidae (hawkers & emperors)	A		A	A		1	A	5
Macromiidae (cruisers)								0
Gomphidae (clubtails)	B			B	A	B	A	5
Libellulidae (darters/skimmers)			A	A		A	A	4
Lepidoptera (aquatic caterpillars/moths)								0

Crambidae (pyralidae)						1	1	
Hemiptera (bugs)							0	
Belostomatidae* (Giant water bugs)							0	
Corixidae* (Water boatmen)			A		B	A	A	4
Gerridae* (Pond skaters/Water striders)					A			1
Hydrometridae* (Water measurers)								0
Naucoridae* (Creeping water bugs)	A			A	A	1	A	5
Nepidae* (Water scorpions)						A	A	2
Notonectidae* (backswimmers)					A			1
Pleidae* (Pygmy backswimmers)					1			1
Veliidae/M...veliidae* (Ripple bugs)		B		A	A	1	B	5
Megaloptera (fishflies, dobsonflies & alderflies)								0
Corydalidae (fishflies & dobsonflies)								0
Sialidae (alderflies)								0
Trichoptera (caddisflies)								0
Dipseudopsidae								0
Ecnomidae								0
Hydropsychidae 1 sp		1						1
Hydropsychidae 2 sp	B		B	B	A			4
Hydropsychidae > 2 sp							B	1
Philopotamidae					A		B	2
Polycentropodidae								0
Psychomyiidae/xiphocentronidae								0
Cased caddis:								0
Barbarochthonidae SWC								0
Calamoceratidae ST								0
Glossosomatidae SWC								0
Hydroptilidae				A		A		2
Hydrosalpingidae SWC								0
Lepidostomatidae	A	A						2
Leptoceridae				A		A	B	3
Petrothrincidae SWC								0
Pisuliidae								0
Sericostomatidae SWC								0
Coleoptera (beetles)								0
Dytiscidae/Noteridae* (Diving beetles)					1			1
Elmidae/Dryopidae* (Riffle beetles)	A					B	A	3
Gyrinidae* (Whirligig beetles)	B	B	B		B	A	B	6
Halplidae* (Crawling water beetles)								0
Scirtidae (Marsh beetles)		B			A			2
Hydraenidae* (Minute moss beetles)				A				1
Hydrophilidae* (Water scavenger beetles)				1				1
Limnichidae (marsh-loving beetles)							1	1
Psephenidae (water pennies)	A			A		A	A	4

Diptera (flies)								0
Athericidae (Snipe flies)					1	A	1	3
Blepharoceridae (Mountain midges)	1		1					2
Ceratopogonidae (Biting midges)	1		A	A	A			4
Chironomidae (midges)	B		B	A	B	B		5
Culicidae* (mosquitoes)	1							1
Dixidae* (Dixid midge)				1		1		2
Empididae (Dance flies)				1				1
Ephydriidae (Shore flies)								0
Muscidae (House flies, Stable flies)	1				1			2
Psychodidae (Moth flies)								0
Simuliidae (blackflies)	A	A		A	B	A	A	6
Syrphidae* (Rat tailed maggots)								0
Tabanidae (Horse flies)						1	1	2
Tipulidae (Crane flies)	A	A		1		A	1	5
Gastropoda (snails)								0
Ampularidae								0
Ancylidae (limpets)								0
Bulininae*								0
Hydrobiidae*								0
Lymnaeidae* (Pond snails)								0
Physidae* (Pouch snails)								0
Planorbinae* (Orb snails)								0
Thiaridae* (=melanidae)								0
Viviparidae* ST								0
Bivalves								0
Corbiculidae (clams)								0
Etheriidae (freshwater oysters)								0
Sphaeriidae (Pill clams)								0
Unionidae (Perly mussels)								0
Sass score	172	62	78	157	143	188	211	340
No. Of Taxa	24	11	12	24	24	29	29	49
Aspt	7,2	5,6	6,5	6,5	6,0	6,5	7,3	6.9

5.2.5. Odonata Assemblage

Adult odonata observed during the October 2025 survey are presented in Table 5-12, which presents 7 of the potential 59 species within the PAOI. The low species diversity could be attributed to seasonality and low flows, limiting emergence of adult odonata.

Table 5-12 Observed adult odonatan during the October 2025 survey

	<p><i>Africallagma glaucum</i> Swamp bluet</p>
	<p><i>Allocnemis leucosticta</i> Goldtail</p>
	<p><i>Chlorolestes fasciatus</i> Mountain malachite</p>

Platycypha fitzsimonsi
Boulder jewel

Paragomphus cognatus
Rock hooktail

Pinheyschna subpupillata
Stream hawker

5.2.6. Fish Assessment

Fish sampling during the survey was conducted using a combination of electroshocking, minnow traps and cast nets, with the sampling effort for each site summarised in Table 5-13. A total of 324 individual specimens were collected, representing six indigenous species (Table 5-14). Based on the frequency of occurrence (FROC) and the expected species list for the region, all anticipated indigenous species were recorded within the Protected Area of Influence (PAOI).

The composition of the fish community closely reflected patterns expected for the geomorphological zones sampled. Upper mountain stream sites, characterised by steep gradients, bedrock dominance and reduced hydraulic diversity, supported low species richness, with assemblages mainly comprising *Chiloglanis anoterus* and *Enteromius crocodilensis*. These two species are well adapted to high-energy environments and ephemeral or seasonally variable flow conditions. Although *Chiloglanis emarginatus* was not collected during the survey, its known distribution is restricted to the lower Ntombe River below the confluence with the Phongolo River. Its absence therefore aligns with known habitat preferences and is not indicative of ecological decline.

A marked increase in richness and abundance occurred at sites situated within upper foothill reaches. Site CFR03 supported five species, CFR05A recorded four species and CFR04 presented the highest diversity with six species. This increase corresponds with greater habitat complexity, improved flow permanence, deeper pools, and the transition toward broader alluvial channel forms, which collectively support a wider range of ecological niches.

The presence of *Labeobarbus nelspruitensis*, a Near Threatened species, at CFR03 and CFR04 further emphasises the conservation significance of the KPE rivers. The occurrence of other large cyprinids, such as *Labeobarbus marequensis* and *Labeobarbus polylepis*, was limited, but their presence is consistent with natural distribution patterns in upper foothill rivers with intermittent deeper pools.

No invasive fish species were recorded during the survey. However, local fishermen reported the presence of *Micropterus nigricans* (largemouth bass) in the Phongolo River. Given the predatory nature and upstream dispersal capability of this species, continued monitoring of potential upstream movement into the Ntombe system is recommended. Any specimens detected upstream of the confluence should be removed to prevent establishment and predation impacts on indigenous species.

Overall, the results indicate that the fish communities within the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment remain in a largely natural state, with diversity patterns closely aligned with geomorphological setting and habitat availability. Images of collected fish species are presented in Table 5-15.

Table 5-13 Sampling effort for fish at each site

Effort	CF01	CFR02B	CFR03	CFR06A	CFR06B	CFR05A	CFR05B	CFR04
Electroshocking (min)	35		45	15	20	35		20
Minnow trap (number traps x time)	1 x 75 min	2 x 140 min		-		2 x 120 min	2 x 140 min	3 x 150 min
Cast Net (throws)				-		4		12

Table 5-14 Fish community results (October 2025)

Species	FROC	CF01	CFR02 B	CFR03	CFR06 A	CFR06 B	CFR05 A	CFR05 B	CFR04
<i>Anoplopterus</i> sp. 'southern stargazer'	5	-	-	3	-	1	8	-	3
<i>Enteromius crocodilensis</i>	5	8	79	23	-	Large schools	64	21	8
<i>Labeobarbus marequensis</i>	5	-	-	-	-	-	Vis. observation	-	18
<i>Labeobarbus polylepis</i>	3	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
<i>Labeobarbus nelspruitensis</i>	5	-	-	6	-	-	-	-	22
<i>Chiloglanis anoterus</i>	5	4	-	18	-	2	23	-	14
<i>Chiloglanis emarginatus</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total Species		2	1	5	0	3	4	1	6
Total Individuals		12	79	51	0	>50	95	21	66

Table 5-15 Photographs of fish species collected within the KPE (October 2025)

Labeobarbus polylepis

Labeobarbus marequensis

Collection of fish at site CFR03

Anoplopterus sp. 'southern stargazer' and the habitat it was collected in at site CFR05A

6. Conclusion

The results of this aquatic biodiversity assessment indicate that the freshwater ecosystems of the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment are in a largely natural to near natural ecological condition, with high habitat integrity, good water quality and diverse biological communities consistent with minimally disturbed mountain and upper foothill systems. Across all surveyed rivers, geomorphological patterns were natural and aligned with expected longitudinal zonation, with steep, bedrock-dominated headwater streams transitioning into moderately confined foothill reaches with increased alluvial influence. These geomorphological characteristics strongly structured the distribution of available biotopes and, in turn, the composition of aquatic communities.

Macroinvertebrate assemblages were diverse and indicated high ecological integrity, with most sites falling within Class A or B ecological categories according to regional SASS5 biological bands. Variation in macroinvertebrate scores reflected natural differences in habitat availability rather than any evidence of water quality impairment. A potentially undescribed species of Leptophlebiidae (*Aprionyx* sp. nov.) was recorded, underscoring the scientific importance of these river systems and the need for future taxonomic investigation.

Fish communities were similarly characteristic of natural mountain and foothill river systems. Species richness increased downstream in line with habitat complexity, and all expected indigenous species were recorded. Importantly, *Labeobarbus nelspruitensis*, a species of conservation concern, was confirmed, and no invasive fish were detected within the KPE. The absence of disturbance-tolerant or alien fishes further supports the conclusion that aquatic habitats within the protected environment remain largely unaltered and self-sustaining.

Water quality across all sites was within natural reference ranges, with no signs of pollution, eutrophication or chemical stress. The consistently low electrical conductivity, circumneutral pH and well-oxygenated conditions reflect an environment with limited anthropogenic influence and healthy catchment processes.

Taken together, the findings confirm that the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment functions as an important refuge for freshwater biodiversity within the broader landscape. The area supports intact ecological processes, high-quality habitat mosaics and species of both regional and conservation significance. These results reinforce the importance of the KPE for provincial and national freshwater conservation priorities, including its contribution to the Enkangala Grassland Strategic Water Source Area and its alignment with multiple Freshwater Ecosystem Priority Area (FEPA) designations.

To maintain this high ecological condition, continued protection of riparian zones, careful management of livestock access, and periodic monitoring of invasive species particularly largemouth bass in downstream systems are recommended. Follow-up surveys targeting specialised macroinvertebrate groups, such as Ephemeroptera, are also encouraged to confirm the presence of the potentially novel species and refine the biodiversity baseline for the area.

Overall, the aquatic ecosystems of the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment remain ecologically functional, biodiverse and minimally impacted, representing a valuable natural asset that requires continued stewardship and conservation attention.

7. References

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